

Study2: Interview Guide

- Can you describe the meaning of security practices in containerization projects?
- Can you tell me how security practices can help to manage container security?
- Can you tell me about the common challenges in risk identification in container systems?
- How do existing security practices assist in detecting security issues within container systems?
- In your opinion, can the current risk identification methods manage the changes AI introduced in the development and deployment of container systems?
- Can you tell me about the challenges in testing containerized applications?
- Based on your experiences, can test results provide insights on how to improve security management practices? Please explain.
- Do you think using AI to develop and deploy container systems requires improvements in the current testing approaches?
- In your opinion, how can logging and monitoring help to manage container system security?
- Do you think current practices used to manage container security ensure the reliability of container system logs?
- Based on your experience, how can analyzing container system logs reflect improvements in current practices used to manage security?
- In your opinion, is human collaboration in a contained project important? And why?
- How can human collaboration be maintained?
- Do you think AI could play a role in maintaining human collaboration in containerized projects? How?
- How can AI be embedded in the current practices used to improve container security?
- What improvements can be made to better share common knowledge on container security issues and effectively incorporate personal experiences?
- How can we improve the understanding of the impact of security practices on system resilience?
- How can we improve knowledge about tools used to manage container and their best practices?
- How can automation in container systems be improved, and in what areas can automation be extended?
- How to improve the standards and guidelines related to container security
- Do you have anything else to add?